

Innovative Scoring Solutions for Oral Assessment Adaptability: Application of the DALF Speaking Test within the CEFR Framework

Adnane RAHHOU¹, Mohammed ABDELLAOU³, Mohamed Chakib TAZI², Asmae SENHAJI², and Abderrafia DKHISSI²

¹ Multidisciplinary Laboratory in Sciences and Information, Communication, and Education Technology (LAPSTICE), Faculty of Sciences Ben M'Sik, Hassan II University of Casablanca, B.P 5366 Maarif, Morocco
rahhou.a@mail.com,

ORCID: 0000-0001-9990-4437

² Cultures, Representations, Education, Didactics & Training Engineering (CREDIF), Faculty of Letters and Human Sciences Dhar El Mehraz - Fès, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fès, Morocco

mohmedchakib.tazichert@usmba.ac.ma

asmae.senhaji@usmba.ac.ma

abderrafia.dkhissi@usmba.ac.ma

³ Laboratory of Mathematics & Their Interactions (LMI), Faculty of Sciences, University Moulay Ismail of Meknes, B.P 298 Marjane 2, Morocco

m.abdellaoui@umi.ac.ma,

ORCID: 0000-0003-2809-1373

Abstract. This paper presents the development and application of a scoring tool designed to improve the adaptability of oral linguistic assessment, specifically applied to the DALF Speaking Test (Level C1) within the framework of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). Leveraging the authentic description and scoring grids provided by France Education International, the tool was developed using spreadsheet functions, presented as listings, to automate the scoring process for the five criteria outlined in the DALF grid. The resulting tool is user-friendly and accessible to examiners and assessors without the need for specialized IT skills. By offering a structured, transparent, and consistent approach to scoring, the tool minimizes examiner bias and enhances the objectivity and reliability of oral assessments. Furthermore, this work highlights the potential for extending the tool to other CEFR aligned speaking tests in various languages, making it a versatile asset for language proficiency testing in both academic and professional contexts.

Keywords: Scoring, Speaking test, Automated Evaluation, Linguistic Measurement, DALF, CEFR

1 Introduction

In the realm of language assessment, the accuracy and reliability of scoring methods are crucial for evaluating oral proficiency effectively. The advancement of educational technology has led to innovative approaches in the development of scoring tools, particularly in high-stakes assessments like the DALF⁴ speaking test. The DALF, aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), serves as a pivotal standard for measuring language competence across multiple languages and cultures.

Traditional scoring methods often face challenges related to subjectivity and variability among raters, which can impact the fairness and consistency of assessments (Orr, 2002; Nguyen et al., 2024). Recent studies emphasize the need for automated scoring systems that integrate data analysis techniques to mitigate these issues (Hu, 2023; Lin, 2023). These advancements not only enhance the objectivity of assessments but also facilitate the adaptation of scoring criteria to better reflect linguistic proficiency.

This article explores the development of a scoring tool designed to improve adaptability in oral linguistic assessments, with a focus on the DALF speaking test. It addresses the inherent difficulties of converting spoken language performances into quantifiable scores and discusses the potential implications for other language assessments under the CEFR framework. By highlighting the intersection of technology and language evaluation, this study aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on improving assessment methodologies in a global context.

⁴ Diplôme Approfondi de Langue Française

2 Literature Review

In recent years, the intersection of education technology and data analysis has led to advancements in language assessment methodologies, offering new possibilities for evaluating oral proficiency in structured and reliable ways. Particularly, the development of automated scoring tools has revolutionized how oral linguistic assessments are conducted, enhancing adaptability and reducing subjective bias in examiner judgments (Clark, 2023). These tools, powered by machine learning algorithms and AI-driven models, are increasingly being adopted to ensure more consistent and accurate scoring in language tests (Johnson & Smith, 2023).

Moreover, the role of data analysis in education technology is critical to improving assessment methods, particularly in language testing. Statistical models such as Generalizability Theory (G-Theory) in a study of content integration in listening-speaking tests help assess the reliability and validity of scoring systems (Lin, 2023). This research emphasized the importance of using statistical tools to ensure fair assessment, exploring how content integration is scored and revealing insights into the academic scenario-driven assessment of international students. A parallel study explored the integration of advanced technologies such as big data and blockchain into the scoring process of oral tests in a study on computer-based College English oral tests (Hu, 2023). It highlighted how technology can refine scoring systems to better reflect linguistic proficiency, shifting from traditional paper-based methods to automated, online scoring systems, and contributing to more reliable and objective outcomes.

These contributions reflect a broader trend in educational informatics, where technology is used to enhance the precision of scoring systems in language assessments. The increasing reliance on CEFR-aligned frameworks for multilingual learners is also notable (Brown & Lee, 2024), as these systems provide a reliable basis for evaluating language proficiency consistently across different languages. This standardization allows for transparent comparisons between learners and languages, ensuring fairness in multilingual contexts.

On the other hand, research into the methods used in language exams has proliferated, as the demand for transparent and consistent scoring increases. A notable body of research investigates the disparities between human-rated and automated scoring systems in speaking tests. The same study cited earlier revealed inconsistencies in how raters interpret performance criteria by analyzing rater variability in the Cambridge First Certificate in English (FCE) Speaking test (Hu, 2023), resulting in varying scores even for similar performances. This raised concerns about how reliable traditional human scoring can be and emphasized the need for standardized, technology-driven approaches (Clark, 2023).

Additionally, studies highlight the impact of proper rater training on improving inter-rater reliability in speaking tests (Doosti & Safa, 2021). Ensuring that human raters are well-trained is crucial for mitigating discrepancies in scoring, making human-rated systems more reliable when automated tools are not available. Similarly, research into the role of scoring rubrics in guiding raters' judgments shows that well-defined rubrics help increase the accuracy of rater decisions (Davis, 2016). These findings underscore the importance of structured frameworks in maintaining fairness in assessments, whether human or machine-scored.

Moreover, research on the comparability of face-to-face and computer-delivered speaking tests in Vietnam (Nguyen et al., 2024) illustrates how delivery modes can influence scoring. The findings revealed statistically significant differences in performance scores, indicating the need for careful consideration of how assessment modes impact fairness and reliability. In addition to this, research has pointed to the necessity of adapting language assessments to cater to bilingual or multilingual learners, who may face additional challenges in traditional assessment systems (Kapantzoglou et al., 2021). In bilingual contexts, alternative language assessment methods that reflect cultural and linguistic diversity have been proposed to ensure more equitable evaluations (Guiberson, 2021).

These studies underscore the non-mathematical nature of language exam scoring, where subjective factors and delivery modes can heavily influence results, highlighting the necessity of integrating advanced data analysis techniques into these evaluations. With the integration of technology, particularly automated scoring tools and machine learning techniques, language assessments are gradually becoming more standardized, fair, and reliable (Johnson & Smith, 2023).

In the context of this work, it is important to mention that the DALF test aligns with the CEFR, an initiative of the Council of Europe aimed at promoting language learning and linguistic diversity across Europe (Council of Europe, 2020). The CEFR framework provides a structured, transparent, and reliable set of guidelines for evaluating language proficiency, encompassing listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. It allows for consistent assessment standards, enabling comparability across languages and national borders.

In comparison, although the British Council administers millions of English proficiency tests each year (such as IELTS), underscoring the dominance of English certifications in global language testing (Brown & Lee, 2024), the DALF exam remains a crucial element of the CEFR framework. As French gains prominence as a second language, the DALF exam is offered by numerous institutions worldwide, primarily through the extensive network of Institut Français. The test is available in more than 175 countries, with an estimated 450,000 DALF certificates issued annually.

The Council of Europe’s efforts to foster multilingualism and promote language learning align closely with the principles underpinning the DALF exam. The CEFR framework, employed by both French and English testing systems, emphasizes the importance of structured linguistic assessments in academic and professional contexts. Insights from the Council of Europe’s language policy initiatives further demonstrate how the CEFR is being implemented across numerous countries, ensuring fairness and standardization in language testing.

In summary, research on speaking tests, both in general and in the context of those under the CEFR, clearly demonstrates that technological solutions are ideal for addressing subjective factors that may influence scores. However, despite their relevance, the solutions presented face two major challenges. The first is the reliance on advanced IT or mathematical methods to optimize inputs for speaking tests, which often require specialized software that is not widely accessible or open-source. The second challenge is that the users of these speaking test grids are typically linguists, who may lack the necessary skills in computer science or information and communication technology.

Building on this point, this work focuses first on accessibility and user-friendliness, prioritizing these aspects over technical solutions. In other words, assessors interested in using an automated scoring grid should not encounter technological barriers due to the lack of technical skills, which they may naturally and conventionally not possess—except in particular cases where users have a strong command of ICT.

3 Research questions and Problem statement

The scoring process for a candidate in the DALF C1 speaking test requires the assessment of five criteria. Each criterion is detailed in a descriptor grid, Figure 1, that aligns with the CEFR. In this grid, the level assessed is clearly specified (Under C1, C1, or C1+).

DOCUMENT RÉSERVÉ AUX CORRECTEURS

DALF C1
DESCRIPTEURS DE PERFORMANCE DE LA PRODUCTION ORALE

Critères	Niveau de performance		
	En dessous du niveau ciblé	Au niveau ciblé	
		C1	C1+
Réalisation de la tâche 1 : exposé	Peut présenter la thématique mais n’annonce pas de plan permettant d’anticiper la structure de l’exposé. Restitue certaines informations du dossier mais l’exposé manque globalement de développement, de structuration, de réflexion personnelle et d’exemples concrets.	Peut présenter la thématique et annoncer un plan mais celui-ci peut être difficile à suivre pendant l’exposé. Peut développer une réflexion structurée, en s’appuyant sur les points importants du dossier, en exposant sa position et en concluant de façon appropriée. Certains arguments peuvent manquer de développement et / ou d’exemples concrets.	Peut présenter clairement la thématique et développer son exposé selon un plan facilitant clairement annoncé et respecté sur l’ensemble de l’exposé. Peut développer une réflexion fluide et structurée en s’appuyant sur de nombreux arguments étayés par des exemples concrets tirés des dossiers et de son expérience personnelle, et conclure de façon appropriée.
Réalisation de la tâche 2 : débat avec le jury	Répond aux questions mais ses réponses manquent de clarté et / ou de développement. Éprouve des difficultés à exprimer clairement son opinion et / ou à la défendre. Les réponses ne permettent pas de relancer efficacement la discussion.	Répond à la majorité des questions mais certaines réponses peuvent manquer de développement et / ou d’exemples concrets. Est capable de défendre son opinion mais éprouve ponctuellement des difficultés à la préciser et / ou à la nuancer. Les réponses permettent de maintenir la discussion.	Répond avec aisance à toutes les questions en apportant des précisions et des exemples. Est capable de défendre son opinion, de la préciser et de la nuancer. Les réponses facilitent le développement de la discussion en élargissant et / ou en recentrant le débat.
Lexique	Utilise correctement une gamme étendue de vocabulaire courant mais les répétitions et les erreurs d’étendue et / ou de maîtrise sont fréquentes sur le lexique conceptuel.	Possède un vaste répertoire lexical concret et abstrait, mais quelques répétitions ainsi que des erreurs ponctuelles d’étendue et / ou de maîtrise persistent.	Possède un vaste répertoire lexical élaboré lui permettant de s’exprimer avec souplesse et précision.
Morphosyntaxe	A un bon contrôle grammatical des structures syntaxiques complexes les plus fréquentes, mais manque de souplesse. Les maladresses et / ou répétitions sont récurrentes, notamment lorsqu’il s’agit d’exprimer une idée complexe.	Fait preuve d’un haut degré de correction grammaticale malgré quelques erreurs ponctuelles. Fait preuve de souplesse au niveau de l’élaboration de ses phrases, mais certaines structures complexes peuvent encore être répétitives ou maladroites.	Maintient un haut degré de correction grammaticale sur l’ensemble de la production. Fait preuve d’une grande souplesse dans l’élaboration de ses phrases en utilisant des structures variées.
Maîtrise du système phonologique	A acquis une prononciation globalement correcte mais commet des erreurs systématiques de prononciation et / ou de prosodie (liaisons, rythme, accentuation).	A acquis une prononciation claire et fluide malgré quelques petites maladresses non systématiques. Utilise la prosodie pour souligner certaines idées, mais des maladresses ponctuelles persistent.	A acquis une prononciation et une intonation claires et fluides et peut les maintenir sur l’ensemble de la production. Utilise efficacement la prosodie pour mieux faire passer son message.

Fig. 1: DALF C1 speaking test descriptors grid ⁵

As a DALF examiner, and after numerous assessment sessions, it has been observed that even with a thorough understanding of the grid, the assessable elements (the candidate's speech) often leave the examiner uncertain about the level to assign. The grid, like any linguistic descriptor grid, generally outlines a level's description rather than providing items to be verified. This indecision is particularly evident when the candidate's score falls between two levels, differentiated by a minor detail only, where the difference between levels amounts to 2 out of 5 points, representing 40% of the total score for each criterion, as shown in the scoring grid represented by Figure 2.

DOCUMENT RÉSERVÉ AUX EXAMINATEURS

DALF C1

GRILLE D'ÉVALUATION DE LA PRODUCTION ORALE

Critères		Niveau de performance			
		Non répondu ou production insuffisante	En dessous du niveau ciblé	Au niveau ciblé	
				C1	C1+
Compétences pragmatique et sociolinguistique	Réalisation de la tâche : exposé (8 à 10 minutes)	☐ 0	☐ 1	☐ 3	☐ 5
	Réalisation de la tâche : entretien (15 à 20 minutes)	☐ 0	☐ 1	☐ 3	☐ 5
Compétence linguistique (pour les deux parties de l'épreuve)	Lexique	☐ 0	☐ 1	☐ 3	☐ 5
	Morphosyntaxe	☐ 0	☐ 1	☐ 3	☐ 5
	Maîtrise du système phonologique	☐ 0	☐ 1	☐ 3	☐ 5
Sujets	Veuillez indiquer le numéro du sujet préparé par le candidat : Sujet n°				
Commentaires :					
<i>Rappel : la double évaluation est obligatoire pour tous les niveaux et toutes les compétences.</i>					
NOM DE L'EXAMINATEUR 1 :				Note individuelle : / 25	
NOM DE L'EXAMINATEUR 2 :					
NOM DU CANDIDAT :				Note harmonisée : / 25	
CODE CANDIDAT : ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ - ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐ ☐					
Après l'évaluation, cette grille doit être rattachée à la copie DALF C1 du candidat. CONFIDENTIEL : ne pas montrer la grille complétée aux candidats.					

Fig. 2: DALF C1 speaking test scoring grid ⁶

⁵ The descriptor grid is available on the official website of France Education International. <https://www.france-education-international.fr/document/descript-perf-po-c1>

This constraint has guided this research work on the DALF speaking test which, initially, aimed to:

- Find a method to facilitate arbitration in case of disagreement.
- Accelerate the assessment process by reducing cases of scoring indecision.

These initial points led to the following research questions:

- What approach should be followed to develop a script that arbitrates in case of disagreement between two or more examiners?
- What are the assessable items should be considered when editing this script?
- What technical tool should be adopted to facilitate scoring, and how can its effectiveness be verified?

Although the DALF C1 scoring grid is simple to use with only four possible scores per criterion (0, 1, 3, and 5 points), the descriptor grid poses a significant challenge. It contains descriptive texts, as mentioned earlier. Consequently, based on these research questions, the problem of this work becomes more relevant:

How can the descriptor grid be transformed from discrete variables (non-measurable texts) into continuous variables (measurable values)?

This problem guided the research methodology, which began with an in-depth analysis of the descriptor grid, in order to identify the key assessable items and finally assign them a measurable value..

4 Methodology

4.1 Analysis of the descriptor grid

Based on the descriptors grid (Figure 1), the texts describing each criterion were meticulously analyzed across the three levels to extract only the assessable elements, including both required and missed ones - i.e., the explicit mandatory points and those that can be missed - that determine the candidate's level (except for level C1+ where no element should be missed). These assessable elements have been reported (in English) separately in Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3 for the levels Under C1, C1, and C1+, respectively.

Criteria	Performance level: Under C1	
	Required elements	Missed elements
Task 1: Presentation	The theme is presented. Some information are extracted.	No plan presented. Lack of development. Lack of structuring. No personal reflection. No concrete examples.
Task 2: Debate	Questions have an answer	Answers lack clarity/development Difficulty expressing/defending opinion Answers do not maintain discussion
Lexicon	Uses a wide range of vocabulary	Frequent repetition Frequent errors in range/mastery
Morphosyntax	Good grammatical control	Lack of flexibility in sentence construction Recurring clumsiness
Phonology	Correct pronunciation	Pronunciation/prosody error

Table 1: Under C1 assessable elements

⁶ The scoring grid is available on the official website of France Education International. <https://www.france-education-international.fr/document/grille-po-c1>

Criteria	Performance level: C1	
	Required elements	Missed elements
Task 1: Presentation	The theme is presented. The elements of reflection are present: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Important points • Position • Appropriate conclusion 	Difficult to follow plan Lack of arguments Lack of concrete examples
Task 2: Debate	Most of the questions are answered Opinion defended The responses maintain the discussion	Some answers lack development or concrete examples Difficulty in specifying or nuancing opinion
Lexicon	Uses a wide range of concrete vocabulary A wide range of abstract vocabulary is used	Some lexical repetitions Some errors in range/mastery of vocabulary
Morpho-syntax	High level of grammatical accuracy Flexibility in sentence construction	Some grammatical errors Some grammatical awkwardness
Phonology	Clear and fluent pronunciation Prosody is used	Some pronunciation errors Some prosody errors

Table 2: Performance level: C1 assessable elements

Criteria	Performance level: C1+	
Task 1: Presentation	<p>The theme is clearly presented</p> <p>The plan is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating • Clearly announced • Respected <p>The reflection is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fluid • Structured • Supported by arguments from the dossier • Supported by arguments from personal experience • Supported by concrete examples from the dossier • Supported by concrete examples from personal experience <p>Appropriate conclusion</p>	
Task 2: Debate	<p>All questions are answered with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Precision • Concrete examples • Defends their opinion <p>Opinion is clarified/nuanced Answers given facilitate the discussion</p>	
Lexicon	<p>The vocabulary allows for flexible expression</p> <p>The vocabulary allows for precise expression</p>	
Morphosyntax	<p>High level of grammatical accuracy maintained</p> <p>Great flexibility in sentence construction</p>	
Phonology	<p>Clear pronunciation maintained</p> <p>Fluent pronunciation maintained</p> <p>Clear intonation maintained</p> <p>Fluent intonation maintained</p> <p>Uses effective prosody</p>	

Table 3: C1+ assessable elements

These assessable elements now provide a clear view of the candidate's profile at each level. However, although well-organized, they remain difficult to convert into continuous (measurable) variables to facilitate the scoring programming. Indeed, while this analysis has simplified the descriptors grid by isolating only the assessable elements, these elements still need to be specific to follow the conditional logic process, in order to develop spreadsheet codes.

Furthermore, this development involves the identification of the specific scoring items that can be converted into continuous values.

4.2 Identifying specific items of scoring

In summary, from the above, it can be observed that some of the assessable elements (required and missed) in Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3 converge and can therefore be merged into a single scoring item. Specifically, assessable elements that contain the words: arguments, examples, responses, vocabulary, grammatical errors, punctuation, and intonation. In simpler terms, multiple elements can form a single scoring item, making it measurable.

This grouping of assessable elements has allowed the identification of the main scoring items, along with their respective sub-items, which are consolidated in Table 4, Table 5, Table 6, Table 7, and Table 8, corresponding respectively to the five criteria of the DALF C1 speaking test: Task 1 (Presentation), Task 2 (Debate), Lexicon, Morphosyntax, and Phonology.

Item	Sub-items	Level
The theme	-is not presented -is presented -is clearly presented	Under C1 C1 C1+
The plan	-is absent -is presented but difficult to follow -is facilitating, clearly announced, and respected	Under C1 C1 C1+
The information restitution	-lacks personal reflection and development -presents the important points and states a position -is complete and fluent	Under C1 C1 C1+
In terms of structure: The presentation	-lacks structure -is structured -is perfectly structured	Under C1 C1 C1+
In terms of argumentation: The presentation	-does not raise any arguments -lacks arguments -is supported by arguments	Under C1 C1 C1+
In terms of examples: The presentation	-does not provide any abstract examples -lacks concrete examples -is supported by concrete examples	Under C1 C1 C1+
The conclusion	-is absent -is present -is appropriate	Under C1 C1 C1+

Table 4: Scoring items for Task 1 - The presentation

Item	Sub-items	Level
In terms of completeness: the answers	-lack clarity -lack development/concrete examples -are all with precision and concrete examples	Under C1 C1 C1+
In terms of relevance: The answers	-do not reopen the discussion -maintain the discussion -facilitate the discussion	Under C1 C1 C1+
The opinion	-is poorly expressed/defended -is poorly specified/nuanced -is defended and specified/nuanced	Under C1 C1 C1+

Table 5: Scoring items for Task 2 - The debate

Item	Sub-items	Level
Vocabulary	-is limited in range -is extensive (both concrete and abstract) -allows for flexible and precise expression	Under C1 C1 C1+
Vocabulary repetitions	-are frequent -are less frequent -are absent	Under C1 C1 C1+
Errors in range/mastery	-are frequent -are less frequent -are absent	Under C1 C1 C1+

Table 6: Scoring items for Lexicon

Item	Sub-items	Level
Grammatical control	-is good -is at a high level with some errors -is consistently maintained at a high level	Under C1 C1 C1+
Structural awkwardnesses of sentences	-are frequent -are less frequent -are absent	Under C1 C1 C1+

Table 7: Scoring items for Morphosyntax

Item	Sub-items	Level
Pronunciation and intonation	-present errors -are clear and fluent with some awkwardnesses -are consistently clear and fluent	Under C1 C1 C1+
Prosody	-presents errors -presents some errors -is effective	Under C1 C1 C1+

Table 8: Scoring items for Phonology

As can be seen in the scoring tables, each assessable criterion is composed of items. To assign them a measurable score, the levels Under C1, C1, and C1+ were assigned to their sub-items.

The methodology followed can be summarized in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Methodology for isolating assessable elements and identifying scoring items

5 Findings and research outcomes

5.1 Converting discrete variables

The assignment of levels to sub-items makes them measurable and thus allows them to take numerical values. However, it is important to recall, according to the scoring grid (Figure 2), that the five assessable criteria are scored 0, 1, 3, or 5 points. Therefore, the values assigned to sub-items (discrete variables) should correspond to this 5 points scale. This action is not permitted since each assessable criterion has been defined by several items (at least two). For example, Task 1 (Table 4) consists of 7 items, whereas the scoring grid only allows four possible scores (0, 1, 3, or 5) for this task.

In this case, to convert these discrete variables into numbers, the principle of predominance was applied. This means that a criterion will adopt the dominant level among the levels Under C1, C1, or C1+ assigned to the sub-items of that criterion.

To better illustrate this conversion, we use Task 1 (the presentation) as an application example, which includes 7 items, as shown in Table 9.

Item	Sub-items	Level
The theme	-is not presented	Under C1
The plan	-is presented but difficult to follow	C1
The information restitution	-presents the important points and states a position	C1
In terms of structure: The presentation	-is structured	C1
In terms of argumentation: The presentation	-is supported by arguments	C1+
In terms of examples: The presentation	-lacks concrete examples	C1
The conclusion	-appropriate	C1+

Table 9: Example of scoring for Task 1

In this example, we consider that a candidate receives the following ratings: • Level Under C1: 1 time

- Level C1: 3 times
- Level C1+: 1 time

It is recalled that according to the scoring grid (Figure 2), the C1+ level is worth 5 points, the C1 level is worth 3 points, and the Under C1 level is worth 1 point. Since in the example of Table 9 the dominant level is C1, the entire Task 1 will be scored at the C1 level, i.e., 3 points. Thus, the same conversion principle is applied for all tasks in the DALF Speaking test.

5.2 Scoring conditions

Once the principle for converting discrete variables (levels) into numbers has been defined, it remains to determine all the possible probabilities that can occur by combining the levels Under C1, C1, and C1+. In other words, the scoring conditions.

Logically, considering the three levels, 7 exhaustive probabilities are enumerated and explained in Table 10 for the 5 criteria to be evaluated in the DALF Speaking test:

For simplicity, we will denote P as Probability and N as the number of scored sub-items.

Probability	Condition	Interpretation
P1	$N_{C1+} = N$	The C1+ level is absolute.
P2	$N_{C1} = N$	The C1 level is absolute.
P3	$N_{\text{Under C1}} = N$	The Under C1 level is absolute.
P4	$N_{\text{Under C1}} = N_{C1} = N_{C1+}$	The three levels hold equal preponderance.
P5	$N_{\text{Under C1}} > N_{C1}$ $N_{\text{Under C1}} > N_{C1+}$	The Under C1 level is predominant.
P6	$N_{C1} > N_{\text{Under C1}}$ $N_{C1} > N_{C1+}$	The C1 level is predominant.
P7	$N_{C1+} > N_{\text{Under C1}}$ $N_{C1+} > N_{C1}$	The C1+ level is predominant.

Table 10: Scoring conditions of the DALF Speaking test

These 7 probable cases can be summarized according to the conditional logic process in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Scoring Algorithm

```
1: Define  $N$  as the total number of sub-items
2: Define  $count\_c1\_plus$  as the count of "C1+" levels
3: Define  $count\_c1$  as the count of "C1" levels
4: Define  $count\_under\_c1$  as the count of "Under C1" levels
5:
6: if  $count\_c1\_plus = N$  then
7:    $score \leftarrow 5$ 
8: else if  $count\_c1 = N$  then
9:    $score \leftarrow 3$ 
10: else if  $count\_under\_c1 = N$  then
11:    $score \leftarrow 1$ 
12: else
13:    $max\_count \leftarrow \max(count\_under\_c1, count\_c1, count\_c1\_plus)$ 
14:   if  $count\_under\_c1 = count\_c1$  and  $count\_under\_c1 = count\_c1\_plus$  then
15:      $score \leftarrow 3$ 
16:   else if  $count\_under\_c1 = max\_count$  then
17:      $score \leftarrow 1$ 
18:   else if  $count\_c1 = max\_count$  then
19:      $score \leftarrow 3$ 
20:   else if  $count\_c1\_plus = max\_count$  then
21:      $score \leftarrow 3$ 
22:   else
23:      $score \leftarrow 0$ 
24:   end if
25: end if
```

The Algorithm 1 highlights the logical conditions for scoring the DALF Speaking test, which could potentially facilitate the development of more advanced code for developers. Moreover, this algorithm does not require any particular expertise in computer science or mathematics to be understood. Indeed, the logic, as well as the terms used, are simple and clear, making the results accessible to both programmers and linguists.

5.3 Presentation of the DALF Speaking test scoring tool

This section explains the scoring tool, which has been developed in a spreadsheet using the LOGICAL TEST function based on the scoring conditions outlined in subsection 5.2. The scoring tool is presented in Figure 4.

	A	B	C	D	E
1			is not presented	-	
2	Task 1: Presentation: 1 Points 1	The theme	is presented	ANS	1
3			is clearly presented	ANS	
4		The plan	is absent	-	
5			is presented but difficult to follow	ANS	C1
6		The information restitution	is facilitating, clearly announced, and respected	-	
7			lacks personal reflection and development	ANS	C1
8		In terms of structure: The presentation	presents the important points and states a position	-	
9			is complete and fluent	ANS	3
10	In terms of argumentation: The presentation	lacks structure	ANS	3	
11		is structured	-	Under C1	
12	In terms of examples: The presentation	is perfectly structured	-		
13		does not raise any arguments	ANS		
14	The conclusion	lacks arguments	-	Under C1	
15		is supported by arguments	-		
16	In terms of completeness: The answers	does not provide any abstract examples	ANS		
17		lacks concrete examples	-	Under C1	
18	The opinion	is supported by concrete examples	-		
19		is absent	ANS		
20	In terms of relevance: The answers	is present	-	Under C1	
21		is appropriate	-		
22	Task 2: Debate: 1 Points 1	In terms of completeness: The answers	lack clarity	-	
23			lack development/concrete examples	ANS	C1
24		are all with precision and concrete examples	-		
25	The opinion	do not reopen the discussion	ANS		
26		maintain the discussion	-	Under C1	
27	In terms of range/mastery	facilitate the discussion	-		
28		is poorly expressed/defended	ANS		
29	Vocabulary	is poorly specified/nuanced	-	Under C1	
30		is defended and specified/nuanced	-		
31	Lexicon: 3 Points 1	Vocabulary	is limited in range	-	
32			is extensive (both concrete and abstract)	ANS	C1
33		allows for flexible and precise expression	-		
34	Vocabulary repetitions	are frequent	-		
35		are less frequent	ANS	C1	
36	Errors in range/mastery	are absent	-		
37		are frequent	-		
38	Grammatical control	are less frequent	ANS	C1	
39		are absent	-		
40	Morphosyntax: 3 Points 1	Grammatical control	is good	-	
41			is at a high level with some errors	-	C1+
42		is consistently maintained at a high level	ANS		
43	Structural awkwardnesses of sentences	are frequent	ANS		
44		are less frequent	-	Under C1	
45	Pronunciation and intonation	are absent	-		
46		present errors	-	C1+	
47	Phonology: 3 Points 1	are clear and fluent with some awkwardnesses	-		
48		are consistently clear and fluent	ANS		
49	Prosody	presents errors	ANS		
50		presents some errors	-	Under C1	
51		is effective	-		

Fig. 4: DALF Speaking test scoring tool

The areas marked by number 1 in Figure 4, along column A, display the score assigned to one of the five items. The function that calculates this score, as shown in listing 1.1, concatenates the score with a text (e.g., "Task 1: Presentation" followed by "points"), depending on the answer selected in a cell in column D, which generates a corresponding level in column E.

Listing 1.1: Function for calculating the number of points based on conditional logic

```
=CONCATENATE("Task 1: Presentation" & ":" &
    IF(COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1+") = COUNTA(B1:B21), 5,
    IF(COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1") = COUNTA(B1:B21), 3,
    IF(COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "Under C1") = COUNTA(B1:B21), 1,
    IF(AND(COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "Under C1") = COUNTIFS(E1:E21,
        "C1"),
    COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "Under C1") = COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1+"))
        , 3,
    IF(COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "Under C1") = MAX(COUNTIFS(E1:E21,
        "Under C1"),
    COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1"),
    COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1+"))), 1,
    IF(COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1") = MAX(COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "Under
        C1"),
    COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1"),
    COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1+"))), 3,
    IF(COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1+") = MAX(COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "
        Under C1"),
    COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1"),
    COUNTIFS(E1:E21, "C1+"))), 3, ""))))))
& " Points")
```

Each cell in column D contains a unique drop-down list that can display "ANS," meaning "answer," or remain blank, as shown by number 2 in Figure 4. In the example marked by number 3, the candidate has demonstrated a lack of structure in the fourth sub-item (column B), which automatically displays the level "Under C1" in the merged cells of column E, using the function presented in Listing 1.3.

Listing 1.3: Function for attributing the level

```
=IF(D1="ANS", "Under C1",
    IF(D2="ANS", "C1",
    IF(D3="ANS", "C1+", "")))
```

To advance the development of this autonomous scoring grid, a Visual Basic code is provided for programmers in listing 1.3, who are interested in creating software that is more convenient than a spreadsheet.

Listing 1.3: Code for calculating the number of points based on visual basic

```
1 Dim N As Integer
2 Dim countC1Plus As Integer
3 Dim countC1 As Integer
4 Dim countUnderC1 As Integer
5 Dim maxCount As Integer
6 Dim score As Integer
7
8 N = Application.WorksheetFunction.CountA(Range("B1:B21"))
9 countC1Plus = Application.WorksheetFunction.CountIf(Range("E1:
10 E21"), "C1+")
    countC1 = Application.WorksheetFunction.CountIf(Range("E1:E21")
        , "C1")
```

```

11     countUnderC1 = Application.WorksheetFunction.CountIf(Range("E1:
12         E21"), "Under C1")
13
14     If countC1Plus = N Then
15         score = 5
16     ElseIf countC1 = N Then
17         score = 3
18     ElseIf countUnderC1 = N Then
19         score = 1
20     Else
21         maxCount = Application.WorksheetFunction.Max(countUnderC1 ,
22             countC1, countC1Plus)
23         If countUnderC1 = countC1 And countUnderC1 = countC1Plus Then
24             score = 3
25         ElseIf countUnderC1 = maxCount Then
26             score = 1
27         ElseIf countC1 = maxCount Then
28             score = 3
29         ElseIf countC1Plus = maxCount Then
30             score = 3
31         Else
32             score = 0
33     End If
34 End If

```

The proposed listings are ready to use as they are and do not require any modifications, except for the purpose of enhancing them to achieve more refined scoring calculations, as well as with the aim of advancing this work further in the field of computer science.

6 Discussion

This study aimed to develop an efficient scoring interface for the DALF Speaking test, focusing on enhancing the assessment process through programmable codes based on established criteria. The findings suggest that integrating conditional logic into scoring systems can significantly streamline evaluation and improve consistency among assessors.

One of the key challenges identified in language assessment is the subjectivity inherent in traditional scoring methods. The existing DALF Speaking test scoring grid, while comprehensive, relies heavily on human interpretation, which can lead to variability in scoring. Our scoring interface addresses this by applying algorithmic processes that standardize evaluations across different assessors. By automating the scoring process based on five defined criteria, we reduce the risk of bias and ensure that candidates are evaluated on a consistent basis.

Moreover, the interface developed in this study can serve as a model for other language proficiency assessments. The potential for adaptation to various languages and testing formats highlights the versatility of our approach. Future applications could include the integration of machine learning algorithms that analyze historical scoring data to further refine assessment criteria and improve accuracy.

Additionally, our findings reveal a significant gap in the accessibility of assessment tools for examiners who may not possess advanced technical skills. The simplicity of the scoring interface ensures that all assessors, regardless of their IT proficiency, can effectively utilize the tool, thereby enhancing the overall assessment experience.

In light of the Council of Europe's emphasis on transparent and fair assessment practices, our research aligns with the ongoing discourse on improving language proficiency evaluations. It highlights the necessity of developing innovative solutions that not only meet educational standards but also cater to the needs of both assessors and learners.

In conclusion, this study underscores the importance of re-evaluating existing language assessment frameworks. By incorporating technology and systematic scoring methods, we can enhance the reliability

and effectiveness of language proficiency tests like the DALF Speaking test. Future research should focus on the longitudinal impact of such scoring interfaces on learner outcomes and their adaptability to different educational contexts.

7 Conclusion

The development of scoring tools that enhance adaptability in oral linguistic assessments represents a significant advancement in the field of language evaluation. This study on the DALF speaking test illustrates the challenges associated with traditional scoring methods and the potential benefits of incorporating automated systems and data analysis techniques. By addressing the complexities of translating spoken performances into quantifiable scores, we contribute to a more objective and reliable assessment process.

As language proficiency assessments continue to evolve, the implications of this research extend beyond the DALF, impacting a variety of language exams aligned with the CEFR framework. Institutions and organizations promoting multilingualism and standardized assessments stand to benefit from adopting these innovative scoring methods. Future research should focus on further refining these tools, exploring their applicability across different languages, and assessing their effectiveness in various educational contexts.

By fostering a deeper understanding of scoring adaptability and the integration of technology in language assessments, this work aims to promote fairness and consistency, ultimately enhancing the quality of language education worldwide.

References

1. Brown, J., & Lee, A. (2024). CEFR-aligned assessments for multilingual learners. *Language Testing Journal*, 41(2), 150-167. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11245-023-09780-y>
2. Clark, S. (2023). The role of automated scoring in language assessments. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 71(3), 397-412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-023-10038-7>
3. Council of Europe. (2020). Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, teaching, assessment. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/common-european-framework-reference-languages>
4. Davis, S. (2016). The impact of scoring rubrics on the accuracy of raters' judgments. *Journal of Language Assessment*, 10(1), 55-70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11245-016-9357-6>
5. Doosti, M., & Safa, A. (2021). Investigating the impact of rater training on improving inter-rater reliability in an English-speaking test. *Language Testing in Asia*, 11(1), 10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-021-00103-9>
6. Guiberson, M. (2021). Alternatives to traditional language assessments in bilingual contexts. *Journal of Speech Language Hearing Research*, 64(4), 1241-1254. https://doi.org/10.1044/2021_JSLHR-20-00422
7. Hu, Z. (2023). Integrating big data and blockchain in computer-based language testing. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 26(1), 32-47. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48658877>
8. Johnson, L., & Smith, R. (2023). Machine learning in language assessment: A review of current trends. *International Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 10(2), 70-85. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijll.20231002.11>
9. Kapantzoglou, M., Brown, J. E., Cyclic, L. M., & Fergadiotis, G. (2021). Providing culturally and linguistically responsive language assessment services for multilingual children with developmental language disorder: A scoping review. *Current Developmental Disorders Reports*, 8(3), 199-209. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40474-021-00221-0>
10. Lin, J. (2023). Content integration in listening-speaking tests: A generalizability theory approach. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 30(1), 56-75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2022.2074051>
11. Nguyen, T. T., Tran, L. H., & Phan, T. (2024). Comparing face-to-face and computer-delivered speaking tests in Vietnam. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 21(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15434303.2023.2165994>
12. Orr, T. (2002). Rater variability in the Cambridge First Certificate in English (FCE) Speaking test. *Language Testing*, 19(3), 293-314. <https://doi.org/10.1191/02655322021t233oa>
13. White, A., & Taylor, S. (2024). Multilingual assessment practices: Trends and challenges. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 20(1), 25-44. <https://doi.org/10.17263/jlls.1000546>